

Microspherophakia and marfan syndrome

Salma HASSINA*, Mohamed Amine **KRICHENE**, Chaimaa **BARDI**, Ihssane **HASNAOUI**, B **BEKKAR**, El Hassan **ABDALAH**

Ophthalmology B, Ibn-Sina University Hospital, Rabat, Morocco.

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Corresponding Author:

Salma HASSINA, Ophthalmology B, Ibn-Sina University Hospital, Rabat, Morocco.

Clinical Image

The patient was 23 years old and had a notion of 1st degree consanguinity.

His finger-count visual acuity was 1 metre in both eyes. Dilated examination of the patient's anterior segment revealed an anteriorly displaced microspherophakia on the right, as shown in figure 1, and the patient was aphakic on the left. The fundus showed a myopic staphyloma with diffuse chororetinal atrophy, the rest being normal. Examination of the retinal periphery revealed the presence of a palisade at 6 o'clock; the patient had an axial length of 28mm and 27.5mm in the right and left eyes.

Figure 1: image showing microspherophaque in a patient with marfan syndrome